

Topic modeling in Telegram channels during the Russia-Ukraine conflict

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Abstract. Telegram has become a preferred platform for far-right activism, conspiracy theories, political propaganda, and misinformation, each with its own target audience. This study investigates the application of multilanguage machine learning techniques for extracting topics from political content on Telegram channels. This research improves the understanding of political information and narratives in different languages on Telegram over time, contributing to the study of digital communication and information warfare within the content of the Telegram channels sphere. Through the exploitation of an extensive dataset on the subject, this work contributes to the state-of-the-art of topic analysis by providing information on prevailing discourses, including the escalating of armed conflicts between Russian and Ukraine, and political tensions in Europe and the USA.

Keywords: Telegram · topic modelling · BERTopic · social networks · propaganda · far-right activism.

1 Introduction

Telegram is currently the fastest-growing social media platform, featuring a wide array of channels on various topics, including political discourse. It is popular not only in post-USSR countries, but also in the Middle East, Europe, and the USA, with more than 800 million monthly active users worldwide and significant numbers from India, Russia, Indonesia, the USA, and Brazil ¹. According to studies on far-right activity on Telegram [24] [5], these types of channel can rank from 5,000 to 300,000 subscribers or more, while some channels have more than 1M followers. Among them, Telegram has become one of the preferred platforms for European and American far-right activism, conspiracy theories,

¹ <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/telegram-users-by-country>

anti-immigrant, anti-feminism discourses, and political extremism among others. [10]. Such groups of channels form an "echo chamber" [16], which can be defined as the far-right core community that has been identified, where continuous reciprocal interactions reinforce shared political biases [7]. In modern information warfare, different governments or political movements can strategically use Telegram to disseminate information to domestic and international audiences who are less engaged with traditional media sources [25]. This platform, especially through its political and news channels, has become a central hub for sharing targeted information, managed by individual or multiple administrators, and is distinguished by its high viewership and citation rate [23]. Telegram has notably evolved into a key medium for broadcasting updates on political events and actions in Ukraine, Russia, Europe, and the USA.

The messenger remains understudied in computer science, with fewer studies on its content and dynamics compared to Twitter or Facebook. Current research faces limitations such as language specificity or focus on particular social-political phenomena, restricting comparative analysis. Furthermore, researchers often use a single approach rather than multiple methodologies [11]. The relevance of the study lies in analysing the diversity of Telegram channels to examine how political content and propaganda evolve across different languages, affiliations, and time periods. Using a fine-tuned BERTopic model and data analysis methods, it assesses the impact of the platform on public opinion, social polarization, its role in modern information warfare, and political mobilisation, addressing Telegram's understudied nature in digital communication research [22].

The paper is structured as follows: in Related Work, the current state of research in the topic modeling on Telegram and social networks is introduced; section Methodology details the methodology employed in this research; the description of the pre-trained fine-tuned BERTopic model and data collection methods are outlined; in Results, the performance of the proposed method is presented, offering a comprehensive analysis of the data and its implications; Conclusions discusses findings within the broader field, drawing connections to existing literature and providing recommendations for further study.

2 Related Work

Although, as we have mentioned, Telegram is a less studied social network compared to others, several works can be found that apply topic modelling to understand the complexity and discourse structure inside this social platform.

Simon et al. [28] applied topic modelling of 362,837 documents to examine the main communities within the Dutch Telegramsphere. The topics were extracted from the Telegram dataset using BERTopic to provide word clusters and OpenAI GPT-4 for natural language interpretations; the dataset was composed by 7,711,975 messages from 10,633 channels by 335,088 unique users (29.9% bots and 70.1% humans) [20] about COVID disinformation. Zehring & Domahidi [31] applied Structural Topic Modelling to 2,497,679 Telegram messages from German anti-COVID and far-right movements, the study found that the

Querdenken movement on Telegram is deeply linked to far-right, QAnon, and alternative media channels, mainly discussing coronavirus conspiracy theories, right-wing populism, and QAnon-related topics.

The Italian and English networks were built and key communities revealed, with their narratives characterised through topic modelling using Anchored Correlation Explanation; the dataset includes 1,980 chats with a total of 8.4 million messages [1]. Sprenkamp et al. [29] developed R2G ("Refugees to Government"), an application using state-of-the-art topic modelling with BERTopic to identify Ukrainian refugee needs from 170,915 messages in 33 Telegram groups to capture text relationships in Ukrainian, Russian, German, and English. Morrell [18] mapped discourse of Russian extremist communities on Telegram, which were identified using LDA and comparing Louvian and Girvan-Newman detection methods, based on 2,731 filtered messages from 19 far-right channels.

BERTopic's performance with various embedding models in preprocessed text was compared [17], revealing its ability to generate meaningful topics from a dataset of 3,286 Serbian tweets about COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy, containing 15 broad topics. Entity and central centroid-based incremental clustering method was empirically shown to outperform existing approaches [21], achieving robust results in processing 500,000 messages on the Twitter Events2012 dataset². Ustyianovych et al. [30] collected text data from VKontakte and performed topic modelling using MLflow with Splunk algorithms. Finally, Russian information narratives from pro-Russian websites were analysed across 5.37 million Reddit comments and 1056 topics identified using the clustering and keyword extraction by BERTopic [9].

The predominance of BERTopic is not surprising. Since its launch in 2022 it has been widely used for its ability to process complex large-scale multilingual textual data in an unsupervised context, for its flexibility and ability to maintain topic coherence over time [26], and has proved to give better results compared with LDA, NMF, and top2vec [4]. Therefore, in this work, the library, with some differential specifications is the one used.

3 Methodology

3.1 Telegram Data

As mentioned before, Telegram channels may be private or public, allowing only administrators to publish posts. Private chats, groups, and channels can interact through message forwarding, displaying the original author [12] and reactions. Reactions to the posts are various emoji that the channel's admin allows users to leave under the post. Telegram API was used to collect publications and their metadata from channels. The collection process generated JSON files containing various media data types, which were stored in MongoDB.

² https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Twitter_event_datasets_2012-2016_/5100460/2

In order to find channels for the dataset, a diverse range of open sources were utilised. This includes references to primary media outlets within each country, government institutions, and political organisations and figures. Channel ratings from platforms TgStat ³ and Tlgrm ⁴, partner channel lists, and forwards from other sources were leveraged. Academic articles on this topic also served as sources [15].

In the computational collection and analysis of Telegram data, it is important to note potential biases from the deletion of messages and entire channels [3]. The dataset consists of 1108 distinct channels in Russian (53.29% of the total dataset), English (16.45%), Ukrainian (10.02%), Spanish (8.88%), German (4.45%), Italian (2.71%), Portuguese (2.30%), and French (1.90%). The corpus of messages covers from 2015 until 1st July 2023. After preprocessing, it comprises 15,994,793 messages, reduced from 18,786,143. Further detailing the dataset’s composition, channels were systematically classified and labeled based on their political orientation and biases (Table 1). Russian-language channels were categorized as pro-Kremlin, anti-Kremlin (opposition), pro-Ukrainian, and neutral. The neutral category includes media and news outlets without discernible political bias. In English, Spanish, French, and other languages, channels are categorized as far-right, pro-Kremlin, and traditional media outlets.

Table 1. Number of messages in the Telegram dataset by languages and political views.

	Far-Right	Pro-Kremlin	Pro-Ukrainian and Anti-Kremlin	Traditional Mass Media and Neutral
English	1,835,023	492,387	27,766	244,488
French	148,742	157,992	-	-
German	510,730	220,459	-	1,265
Italian	122,417	284,277	-	-
Portuguese	285,978	77,114	12,049	2,347
Russian	-	5,782,860	2,070,127	657,779
Spanish	526,024	132,047	20,495	779,778
Ukrainian	-	3,349	1,599,300	-

3.2 Topic modelling

Following best practices, incremental learning ("Online Topic Modelling") was used to continuously adapt to new data [6]. This approach minimizes memory usage, integrates new data without full retraining, and dynamically identifies new

³ <https://tgstat.ru/>

⁴ <https://tlgrm.ru/channels>

topics⁵. The framework (Figure 1) includes the BERT Embedding model, Incremental PCA (IPCA) as Dimension Reducer, MiniBatchKMeans as Clustering Engine, Vectorizer Model, and KeyBERT representation model.

Preprocessing data The multilingual corpus of Telegram messages poses challenges in data preparation due to the variety of languages, document sizes, and content diversity. Initially, all documents were normalized and cleaned to remove emojis, URLs, and irrelevant languages, e.g. Arabic or Hebrew. Documents were lemmatized to handle the grammatical complexities of Russian and Ukrainian, ensuring the model does not mistake similar words with different endings as distinct. Preprocessing also involved removing empty messages, duplicates, and messages with 5 words and fewer.

Model Application The model initiates the process by extracting embeddings using pre-trained models, such as Sentence-Transformers, then reduces dimensional to enhance clustering. The process concludes by organising embeddings into clusters that represent potential topics. The "paraphrase-multilingual-MiniLM-L12-v2" embedding model is selected for its proficiency in generating semantically wide representations across more than 50 languages (including Ukrainian). This model maps sentences to a 384-dimensional dense vector space and it has 117M parameters.

Fig. 1. Workflow and details of our BERTopic architecture.

OnlineCountVectorizer pre-processes documents by transforming text into a token count matrix. Filters, including a minimum document term frequency of 5 and a maximum document frequency of 50%, focus on relevant terms. A decay factor of 0.01 adjusts term significance based on occurrence rate. Stop words from the SpaCy library eliminate less informative terms. The IPCA reduces embeddings to 50 principal components, capturing significant data variance while being memory efficient for handling 15.9M messages and avoiding topic overlap. IPCA maintains continuity of principal component values over

⁵ https://maartengr.github.io/BERTopic/getting_started/online/online.html

sequential updates, ensuring data consistency [14]. The MiniBatchKMeans algorithm, optimised for large datasets through stochastic gradient descent, was used for clustering. The elbow method determined 150 as the optimal number of clusters by identifying a point where the decrease in within-cluster sum of squared errors slows down significantly [27]. Using a fixed zero random state ensures replicability⁶. While MiniBatchKMeans might slightly underperform in cluster tightness, it offers significant speed and scalability advantages [19]. In an online topic modeling, document chunks were processed iteratively, updating the topic model to maintain relevance and accuracy. A class-based TF-IDF procedure maintains topic coherence over time, allowing the model to adapt to new data in dynamic settings, and after training, the fine-tuned KeyBERTInspired representation model was employed with the CountVectorizer to filter out stop words [8].

Model Evaluation Extracted topics were evaluated based on keyword frequency, Topic Coherence, and Topic Diversity. The Coherence Model, using the ‘c_v’ measure from the Gensim library, assesses semantic similarity between high-scoring words to gauge topic quality. Coherence scores were aggregated for an average across Telegram channels. The diversity score, calculated as the ratio of unique words to total words across topics, provides insight into the model’s ability to generate meaningful and distinct topics.

4 Results

Results show a Coherence Score of 0.646, indicating a medium level of semantic similarity between topics, suggesting that the defined topics are meaningful and the words within each topic likely share a common context. 150 thematic clusters were obtained, which were received in different languages, predominantly Russian and Ukrainian, the results were translated with Deepl translator library. Additionally, the Topic Diversity score of 0.485 reflects a moderate level of uniqueness across the topics. Moreover, as the number of clusters decreases, the topic diversity metric, which indicates the variety of topics in the trained model, also diminishes. The 12 most representative topics represent 20.02% of all dataset (Figure 2), it demonstrates the most frequent terms in largest topics, indicating weight of each term in the topic. These topics are repetitive and concern the politics of Ukraine and Russia, the details of the armed conflict. Table 2 shows examples of Telegram’s messages with information about views and reactions.

Figure 3 shows the most popular topics and their frequency ratio by political view for each language. Pro-Kremlin topics are predominantly discussed in Russian sources and they are also prevalent in German and French sources, indicating cross-linguistic influence. Topic 2, one of the most frequent, mostly

⁶ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.cluster.MinibatchKMeans.html>

Fig. 2. Word Scores of the Most Frequent Topics and Their Percentage of the Entire Dataset.

appears in Russian Pro-Kremlin sources. Neutral and Russian opposition topic 64 (‘russia’, ‘ukraine’, ‘moscow’, ‘kazakhstan’, ‘belarus’, ‘detention’) mentions political arrests in CIS countries (Kazakhstan and Belarus). Pro-Ukraine topics in Russian and Ukrainian show the most frequent topic 89. Pro-Kremlin topic 139 highlights news of missile or drone attacks on Ukrainian and Russian cities (‘moscow’, ‘kharkiv’, ‘ukraine’, ‘road’, ‘report’, ‘vsu’⁷, ‘shelling’), focusing on specific cities and events.

Topics in Far-Right and Traditional Mass Media (Traditional) demonstrate a diverse range of interests. Topic 18 (‘fbi’, ‘trump’, ‘president’, ‘indictment’) is prevalent in Far-Right English sources and topic about elections is in Traditional Mass Media. Vaccine discussions topic during the COVID-19 pandemic is relevant for Far-Right German and French channels. Topics 108 (‘republican’, ‘democrat’, ‘political’, ‘election’, ‘voter’) and 68 (‘tweet’, ‘clip’, ‘protest’, ‘patriotfront’⁸, ‘social’, ‘post’, ‘peace’, ‘activist’, ‘trump’) are primarily found in

⁷ Ukrainian Army

⁸ Patriot Front is an American white supremacist and neo-fascist hate group

Italian and Portuguese sources within the Far-Right, indicating regional interests in right-wing politics.

Fig. 3. The most popular topics on languages and political views.

The Figure 4 changes in the popularity of topics and their growth in scope (frequency of mentions in documents) over time by quarter. It demonstrates a significant rise in discussions related to Russia and Ukraine, particularly peaking in early 2022, which corresponds with the onset of the conflict. Topic 13 appears in Q1 2020, and topic 89 culminates in significant spikes in Q1 2022 and Q2 2022. Similarly, topics 74 and 110 associated with 'missile', 'shell', 'artillery', 'fighter', 'ammunition' surged in Q2 2022, reflecting the escalation of military actions in Ukraine. Discussions on 'coronavirus' and related terms dominated earlier periods, particularly in 2020, indicating the global impact of the pandemic. Moreover, the figure highlights trump' in Q1 2021, which was relevant because of the growth of the QAnon movement [13]. Other topics, such as 'inflation' and 'economy', influenced by economic repercussions of the pandemic and geopolitical tensions.

Fig. 4. Most Popular Topic by Quarter.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, BERTopic was utilized to analyze and categorize topics in Telegram channels, providing insights into the distribution and characteristics of content across various topics and time periods. The BERTopic analysis revealed a medium level of semantic similarity and a moderate level of uniqueness across 150 identified topics, encompassing key themes such as the Russian-Ukrainian political and armed conflict and the confrontation between Trump and Biden. The analysis demonstrated how the essence of posts in Telegram channels varied. This comprehensive approach allowed to obtain of the frequency and popularity of topics. Despite these promising results, limitations were noted, including the over-representation of Russian language content and the focus on specific topics like the armed conflict between Russia and Ukraine. One possible consequence of this is overlapping clusters, that can also be a consequence of applying the K-means method [2]. On the other side, the occurrence of similar topics in BERTopic models is due to the high granularity which allows the model to capture subtle nuances and variations within the data, enhancing the ability to explore and understand the information more comprehensively.

Future research should aim to extend the language segments of Telegram channels, include additional metadata for a more thorough data analysis, and application of multi-language pre-trained classification machine learning models, to detect and measure toxicity in political content on Telegram channels. Further validation with larger and more diverse datasets will be essential to generalize these findings and enhance the robustness of the analysis.

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Table 2. Examples of Telegram messages and their statistics

Topic	Message	Views	Reactions
89	I have awarded the title of Hero of Ukraine to Oleksandr Matsievskyi. A man who will be known by all Ukrainians for his bravery and for his "Glory to Ukraine!" - Zelensky.	1186431	31244
2	After yesterday the Russian Defence Ministry officially confirmed the information of the head of the PMC "Wagner" about the capture of Bakhmut, and the Kremlin reported that Vladimir Putin congratulated the PMC and the Russian Armed Forces on this event, Ukraine does not recognise the loss of the city.	13899	811
122	Russia's president, Vladimir Putin, was the fourth highest rated by the same Americans surveyed, a remarkable fact given the Western media campaign against the Eurasian country in the wake of the conflict in Ukraine.	10389	725
74	The military administration told how many missiles were launched at Zaporizhzhia: one of the missiles got stuck in the roof - inclusion.	6576	135
13	Putin's "cook" denies Kremlin's claims about Russia's war with NATO in Ukraine - ISW. He noted that Russia is fighting "exclusively with Ukrainians" equipped with NATO-provided equipment and some "Russophobic" mercenaries who voluntarily support Ukraine, but not with NATO itself.	403663	10875
110	The composition of Russian assault units is based on an analysis of Russian military doctrine.	60864	1373
64	A court in Kazakhstan has arrested Dmitry Kozak, a 19-year-old Russian anarchist detained at Moscow's request.	19410	251
104	Putin answered the question that a lot of people have been asking for the last year: Why didn't Russia start the SMO back in 2014, when the Ukrainian army was weak.	5940	231
103	"Of course, you can build abstruse schemes, as the intellectual Shepherd does. But life is banal: Russia is a post-Soviet country. The collapse of the Soviet Union had a delayed result. Take into account that the Ukrainian and Russian parties ruled the USSR and competed with each other. What Yeltsin avoided, Putin could not avoid."	72083	1117
31	Taliban bring armoured vehicles to the border with Iran. Local sources say that tanks, light armoured vehicles and large detachments of the Taliban movement are concentrated in the Eslam-Kale border crossing area on the border between Iran and Afghanistan.	4809	124
58	Putin is working in the Kremlin today despite yesterday's drone attack. There are no changes in his schedule, Peskov said. The press secretary said that the president remains calm, collected and clear in his assessments and commands against the background of the drone attack. No special address by Putin to Russians is planned.	217152	1870
116	The plane carrying Chinese President Xi Jinping has landed at Moscow's Vnukovo airport. The Chinese leader will stay in the capital for three days: he is expected to have several meetings with Russian President Vladimir Putin and members of the government.	8120	279